

Process control and modelling

Advanced process control and CFD modelling for optimizing PCERs operation

ABSTRACT

Modelling using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is a powerful tool for guiding the process design as well as the optimization of the operating conditions of different system. In the SINGLE project, CFD modelling is used for the optimization of the design at cell and stack level, studying the cell connectivity (electrical and gas-flow) and reaction conditions to maximise reaction yield, electrochemical performance and energy efficiency. In addition, CFD simulations are also used as a support in the development and validation of the advanced control model.

The designed control system will guarantee the set recovery, maximum hydrogen production, adaptation to the available power and real-time monitoring for maximum safety.

Key points

- CFD modelling optimise the cell and stack design and operating conditions.
- Real-time monitoring of the most relevant variables ensures safe operation.
- Optimal operation permits to maximize hydrogen production.
- The control strategy makes the PCER adapt to the available electric power.

Related KERs or Info-packs

- Info-packs #1 to #3

Introduction

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is a valuable tool for system design and operational optimization. In the SINGLE project, CFD modelling has focused on the optimization of cells and stack design, cell connectivity (electrical and gas-flow) and reaction conditions to maximise reaction yield, electrochemical performance and energy efficiency.

The CFD models incorporate key reactor processes, including gas flow dynamics, chemical reactions, mass transport, electrochemistry, and heat transfer. While the 2D/3D CFD models are important for understanding the detailed performance of cells and stacks, they are computationally expensive and unsuitable for control system modelling. Therefore, efficient surrogate control-oriented models have been developed, using the CFD simulations to validate and calibrate them.

Based on the surrogated models, the control system is designed at cell and stack level, showing its capacity for safe and efficient dynamic operation.

In the SINGLE project, a **multiphysics modelling strategy** has been developed to optimize cell and stack design and operation, aiming to achieve **10 kg H₂/day production**. High-fidelity models have been used to integrate coupled phenomena such as gas flow, chemical reactions, mass transport, electrochemistry, heat transfer, and mechanical stresses.

These models enable **detailed analysis of how local conditions within the cells impact overall electrochemical performance**. Simulations carried out using Comsol Multiphysics have been key to improving cell and stack configuration, electrical and gas-flow connectivity, and reaction conditions.

The models provide critical insights, including voltage/current distribution, temperature profiles, gas velocity, and species distribution across different reactor zones. These results help identify performance-limiting factors and support decisions for safe, efficient, and sustainable operation. Moreover, multi-objective optimization can be applied to address additional goals such as **flexibility, environmental impact, and safety under varying operational conditions**.

The main objectives of the control system are:

- **Optimality:** the control algorithms make the device autonomously and optimally balance between H₂ recovery, H₂ production and energy efficiency.
- **Load following capabilities:** given that the device is expected to operate alongside intermittent and time-varying renewable energy sources, the control algorithm is capable of dynamically adapt the device to these fluctuating power inputs.

In parallel to these objectives, the following properties have been considered:

- **Robustness:** the control algorithm accounts for uncertain or unmodeled phenomena, such as unanticipated heat exchange with the environment and uncontrolled pre-cracking in the feed flow.
- **Safety:** the algorithm ensures the system avoids conditions that could pose risks to the device or nearby individuals.

Conclusions

Real-time dynamic optimization driven by the control algorithms has shown to be effective for hydrogen production improvement, keeping the PCER inside a safe operating region.

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